

TRANSLATION PECULIARITIES OF THE ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS INTO UZBEK

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Abstract. The article analyzes the translation methods and ways of the English phraseological units. Some challenges in translation of set expressions are researched and distinct solutions are proposed in order to tackle their translation problems.

Keywords: Phraseological unit, set expression, stable word combination, deduce, semantic relationship, figurative meaning, equivalents, literalism, norm of a language.

Phraseological units (set expressions) form stable lexical units. Their meaning is not deduced from the separate meanings of the components, but from the meaning of the whole combination. For example, *it is high time* – *vaqt bo‘ldi*, *take your time* – *shoshilmang*, *help yourself* – *olib o‘tiring*.

From the point of view of the level of semantic relationship of their components, set expressions are divided into two, i.e., expressions with figurative meaning and expressions with dictionary meaning [1, 63 p.].

The elements of expressions with dictionary meaning can preserve their lexical meanings even in the combination, but they can combine only with certain words to form a combination. For example, *to take measures* – *chora ko‘rmoq*, *to make a decision* – *qaror qabul qilmoq*. Sometimes there are synonyms of such word combinations. For example, *to take a decision*.

This situation testifies to the fact that set expressions may not always be fixed combinations. For example, “*to achieve results*” can also have the variant of “*to accomplish results*”.

But in most cases, they are a stable phrase. For example, *pay attention* – *e‘tibor bermoq*, *draw (smb’s) attention* – *e‘tiborni tortmoq*.

The translation of phraseological units with a dictionary meaning is carried out in two ways:

1) Fixed units based on a noun phrase. For example, *to take a chance*, *to have a rest*, *to take offense*, *to take a nap*.

2) with equivalent combinations (absolute and partial):

a) complete equivalents: *to hit the target* – *mo‘ljalga urmoq*, *to put an end to* – *nuqta qo‘ymoq*, *tugatmoq*, *to play with fire* – *olov bilan o‘ynashmoq*, *the root of the trouble* – *yovuzlik ildizi*.

b) partial equivalents: *to take into account* – *e‘tiborga olmoq*, *to make a point* – *alohida e‘tibor qaratmoq*, *to jump at conclusions* – *darhol xulosa qilmoq*, *moment of silence* – *sukut onlari*, *trouble shooter* – *ziddiyatlar kushandasi*, *token strike* – *ogohlantiruvchi ish tashlash (token – belgi, ramz)*.

Phraseological units are an integral part of the English language, and knowing them is very essential for creating an equivalent translation [2, 78 p.].

Several similar phrases in the English language are confused due to the absence of articles or the use of different prepositions. Pay attention to the following pairs: *in case of* – *sodir bo‘lganda*, *in the case of* – *ga kelsak*, *in (the) face of* – *mavjudligida*, *on the face of* – *dan kelib chiqib*, *in favour of* – *ning foydasiga*, *in favour with* – *ni tasdiqlab*, *for fear of* – *bo‘lmasligi uchun*, *in fear of* – *dan qo‘rqib*, *by the name of* – *nomi ostida*, *in the name of* – *ning nomidan*.

Regardless of the degree of connection between the components of stable units, the main rule in translation should be to follow to the norms of the translation language, that means we should not allow literalism in translation and not violate the rule of word combinations in the translation language.

Fixed combinations or phraseological units with a figurative meaning are known as *idioms*. An idiom is a stable word combination (speech unit), the meaning of which cannot be deduced from the meanings of its components, but from the general meaning of the combination.

English, like any other languages, is rich in peculiar idioms. The components of idioms have lost their initial dictionary meaning, and the meaning is not deduced from the meaning of the individual components: ***through thick and thin*** – *nima bo'lsa ham*, ***tooth and nail*** – *tish tirnog'i bilan kirishmoq*, ***it's raining cats and dogs*** – *yomg'ir chelaklab quymoqda*, ***to be caught red-handed*** – *jinoyat ustida qo'lga olinmoq*.

When translating English idiomatic units, their equivalents in Uzbek and Russian languages are tried to be found. They can be rendered in the following ways:

(1) with complete equivalents. If the expressions have an international character, complete equivalents can be found in translation: ***to play with fire*** – *olov bilan o'ynashmoq*. ***to bring oil to fire*** – *alangaga yog' quymoq*.

(2) with relative equivalents. If there are some differences in keeping the meaning of English idioms in Uzbek, relative equivalents are used: ***to show one's teeth*** – *darg'azab bo'lmoq*.

(3) with completely different lexical means called phraseological analogues:

a) in the translation of proverbs: ***East or West home is best***. *O'z uying o'lan to'shaging. Make hay while the sun shines. Temirni qizig'ida bos. A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush. Uzoqdagi xashakdan yaqindagi somon yaxshi.*

b) in the translation of figurative expressions: ***to make a mountain out of a molehill*** – *pashshadan fil yasamoq*, ***to beat about the bush*** – *gapni aylantirmoq*.

(4) with descriptive translation. When there is no suitable equivalent or analogue in the Uzbek language, a figurative translation is used: ***to show the white feather*** – *ichidan zil ketti*. [3, 189 p.]

The above English examples are typical of all fields of life. Undoubtedly, all professions have their own peculiar idioms. Descriptive translation is frequently used in rendering the meaning of idioms related to different fields. For example, the following phraseological units are characteristic of finance and business:

creeping takeover,
tape dancing (US),
triple witching hour.

Sometimes phraseological units are completely compatible with free word combinations, so the translator needs to be very attentive in understanding their meaning in the context and creating an adequate translation:

to sit on the fence – *panjara ustida o'tirmoq (sitting on the fence) also, kutib qolmoq (to wait long)*.

red tape – *qizil tasma (red ribbon), also buyruqbozlik (bureaucracy)*.

yellow pages – *sariq sahifalar (yellow color pages), also, tashkilotlar haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan telefon ko'rsatmalari kitobchasidagi sariq sahifalar (the yellow pages in the telephone directory with information about organizations)*.

red herring – *dudlangan baliq* (smoked fish) or *e'tiborni tortish harakati* (the act of attracting attention), (to draw a red herring across the path – *e'tiborni tortmoq*).

Regarding the subject of phraseology, it should be noted that sometimes the translator is faced with the translation of specific national idioms. Translating specific national idioms requires understanding the cultural context. Literal translation of national idioms occurs only when its meaning is known and popular in the translated language, for example:

Rome was not built in a day.

Rim bir kunda qurilmagan.

In the remaining cases, it is necessary to look for a neutral or oral (depending on the style) equivalent in the translation, and translators should avoid national colored expressions in the Uzbek and Russian languages. For the translation of the fixed expression “*to carry coal to Newcastle*” we can use “*o'rmonga o'tin bilan bormoq*” in Uzbek as an equivalent:

Will you carry coal to Newcastle?

O'rmonga o'tin bilan borasanmi?

Unique national idioms can be translated both in the form of simple neutral lexis and in the form of set expressions:

to be from Missouri – *har narsaga shubha bilan qarash* (to look at everything with suspicion).

to grin like a Cheshire cat – *og'zi qulog'ida bo'lmoq* (to give a big smile).

he will not set the Thames on fire – *u osmondagi oyni olib berolmaydi* (He cannot bring the moon in the sky).

From the translator's point of view, no matter how diverse the specific qualities of phraseological units are, no matter how much the relationship between their components is, the main rule in translation is to follow the norms of the translation language, that is, to avoid literalism and it should not violate the rule of word combinations in the translated language.

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